

Bird Blood DNA for ONT Sequencing: Pilot Project

Summary

The aim of the pilot project was to determine:

1. The smallest volume of bird blood (nucleated blood) that can be used to isolate DNA of sufficient quantity and quality to generate good quality Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) sequencing data.
2. The most suitable DNA extraction kit for isolating DNA for sequencing.
Oxford Nanopore long-range sequencing has very specific DNA requirements. For submission of DNA to the 1KSA program, the minimum requirements are:
 - As much DNA as possible ($>1 \mu\text{g}$ of dsDNA as measured by Qubit at a minimum concentration of $100 \text{ ng}/\mu\text{l}$)
 - Purity ratios as measured by Nanodrop of $A260/A280 = 1.8$ and $A260/A230 = 2 - 2.2$
 - Average fragment size $>10 \text{ kb}$ as measured by Agilent TapeStation, gel or equivalent
3. The most suitable storage methods for bird blood during ambient temperature shipping.

The results indicate that:

1. The smallest volume of blood that provides both sufficient quantity and quality of dsDNA is $2 \mu\text{l}$ of whole blood. Therefore $20 \mu\text{l}$ of blood in a 1:10 dilution for storage can be used for DNA extraction. However, the recommended volume is $5 \mu\text{l}$ of whole blood, so $50 \mu\text{l}$ of blood in a 1:10 dilution for storage. This is due to quantity and quality variation in extractions and the quality requirements for sequencing. For higher yields, it is suggested that the $5 \mu\text{l}$ of whole blood (diluted 1:10 to a volume of $50 \mu\text{l}$) be split into two DNA extractions and pooled.
2. The Invitrogen PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit provides pure and intact DNA of sufficient quality for ONT sequencing. The elution buffer provided with the kit proved suitable for direct use in the first step of ONT library preparation.
The Macherey-Nagel NucleoBond® HMW DNA kit is more suitable for larger sample volumes such as 10 to $25 \mu\text{l}$ of whole blood (100 to $250 \mu\text{l}$ when diluted 1:10 in storage solution).
3. EDTA tubes (first choice) or Ethanol work well to preserve the bird blood for DNA extraction and long read sequencing on the ONT platform. These are the recommended storage methods.

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Submission Details

Type of Organism: Bird (parakeets)

Parakeet 1 Light green

Parakeet 2 Yellow

Parakeet 3 Black tip, orange eye ring

Parakeet 3 was not used for DNA extractions

Sample type submitted: Bird blood

Collection date: 13 February 2026

Date received: 23 February 2026

Number of samples submitted: 60

Storage methods: Ethanol, FTA paper, Acetone, EDTA (purple tube), DNA/RNA shield

See Table 1 for a list of samples.

Table 1: Bird blood sample details

Tube	Sample	Bird	Treatment	Treatment #
1	Parakeet 1 EtOH	Parakeet 1	Ethanol	T1
2	Parakeet 1 EtOH	Parakeet 1	Ethanol	T1
3	Parakeet 1 EtOH	Parakeet 1	Ethanol	T1
4	Parakeet 1 EtOH	Parakeet 1	Ethanol	T1
5	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	FTA paper	T2
6	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	FTA paper	T2
7	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	FTA paper	T2
8	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	FTA paper	T2
9	Parakeet 1 ACE	Parakeet 1	Acetone	T3
10	Parakeet 1 ACE	Parakeet 1	Acetone	T3
11	Parakeet 1 ACE	Parakeet 1	Acetone	T3
12	Parakeet 1 ACE	Parakeet 1	Acetone	T3
13	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
14	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
15	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
16	Parakeet 1	Parakeet 1	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
17	Parakeet 1 SHE	Parakeet 1	DNA/RNA shield	T5
18	Parakeet 1 SHE	Parakeet 1	DNA/RNA shield	T5
19	Parakeet 1 SHE	Parakeet 1	DNA/RNA shield	T5
20	Parakeet 1 SHE	Parakeet 1	DNA/RNA shield	T5
21	Parakeet 2 EtOH	Parakeet 2	Ethanol	T1
22	Parakeet 2 EtOH	Parakeet 2	Ethanol	T1
23	Parakeet 2 EtOH	Parakeet 2	Ethanol	T1
24	Parakeet 2 EtOH	Parakeet 2	Ethanol	T1
25	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	FTA paper	T2
26	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	FTA paper	T2
27	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	FTA paper	T2
28	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	FTA paper	T2
29	Parakeet 2 ACE	Parakeet 2	Acetone	T3
30	Parakeet 2 ACE	Parakeet 2	Acetone	T3
31	Parakeet 2 ACE	Parakeet 2	Acetone	T3
32	Parakeet 2 ACE	Parakeet 2	Acetone	T3
33	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
34	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
35	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
36	Parakeet 2	Parakeet 2	EDTA (purple tube)	T4
37	Parakeet 2 SHE	Parakeet 2	DNA/RNA shield	T5
38	Parakeet 2 SHE	Parakeet 2	DNA/RNA shield	T5
39	Parakeet 2 SHE	Parakeet 2	DNA/RNA shield	T5
40	Parakeet 2 SHE	Parakeet 2	DNA/RNA shield	T5
41 – 60: Parakeet 3 was not used for DNA extractions				

DNA Extraction & Quality Control

Storage Methods

The treatments/storage methods were prepared according to Figure 1.

Treatments (100 μ l blood per treatment)

T1: EtOH \times 4 (25 μ l blood + 225 μ l EtOH) - use 10 μ l for extraction

T2: FTA paper \times 4 (25 μ l blood drops)

T3: Acetone \times 4 (25 μ l blood + 225 μ l Acetone) - use 10 μ l for extraction

T4: EDTA \times 4 (25 μ l of blood + 225 μ l of EDTA) - use 10 μ l for extraction

T5: DNA/RNA shield \times 4 (25 μ l blood + 225 μ l DNA/RNA shield) - use 10 μ l for extraction

Figure 1: Plan for bird blood sampling and storage

The treatments/storage methods were visually assessed before DNA extractions commenced.

Ethanol:

The blood was clotted. The tubes contained different volumes of ethanol, all below 220 μ l, indicating Ethanol had evaporated, even with the protection of Parafilm®.

Any remaining ethanol was removed after pelleting the clotted blood. The blood was suspended in 225 μ l 1 \times Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS). The clotted blood was difficult to suspend and pipette making the amount of blood used for DNA extraction less accurate.

FTA paper:

FTA paper with blood spots appeared as expected.

Acetone:

The blood was dried indicating the acetone evaporated, even with the protection of Parafilm®. The blood was suspended in 225 μ l 1 \times PBS. It went into solution easily.

EDTA tube:

Vacuare EDTA K2 tubes were used. These contain dipotassium EDTA spray-dried on the tube walls:

The volumes in the tubes differed and the blood was too viscous to pipette. Therefore 225 μ l 1 \times PBS was added.

DNA/RNA Shield:

Volume was approximately 250 μ l as expected.

DNA Extractions

Macherey-Nagel NucleoBond® HMW DNA Kit

Initially DNA was extracted from 10 µl of diluted bird blood stored in EDTA and Ethanol. The manufacturer's protocol was followed (<https://www.mn-net.com/media/pdf/1b/f4/18/Instruction-NucleoBond-DNA-HMW.pdf>). The extraction from the Ethanol storage treatment failed (Table 2, tube 21) and the EDTA stored blood (diluted) DNA extraction produced too little DNA for downstream processing (Table 2, tube 33). Therefore 100 µl of stored blood was tested from Ethanol and EDTA treatments. The extraction of DNA from Ethanol-stored blood failed again, but the EDTA-stored DNA extraction produced a sufficient quantity and quality of DNA.

Further testing was carried out on 10, 20 and 50 µl volumes of stored blood to determine the lowest suitable volume for extractions with the NucleoBond® kit. Results were suboptimal, or failed, except for the DNA/RNA Shield treatment (Table 2, tube 39).

The protocol was adjusted by diluting 250 µl of the 1:10 diluted blood (Ethanol and Acetone treatments) further to 2 ml with 1 × PBS and incubating it on ice for 30 min. The Isopropanol precipitation step was transferred to 1.5 ml tubes in order to centrifuge at a higher speed (~11 000 × g) to pellet the DNA more efficiently and avoid losing the DNA pellets. This method successfully produced DNA suitable for downstream processing (Table 2, tubes 3 and 9).

In conclusion, the NucleoBond® HMW DNA kit worked well for Acetone, EDTA and DNA/RNA Shield samples. However, a large volume of blood (25 µl whole blood; 250 µl 1:10 diluted blood) was required.

Invitrogen PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit

Initially DNA was extracted from 10 µl of bird blood stored in EDTA and Ethanol (1 µl whole blood). The manufacturer's protocol was followed (https://documents.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/LSG/manuals/purelink_genomic_mini_man.pdf). The extractions from the Ethanol and EDTA treatments (Table 2, tubes 1 and 13) produced barely sufficient yield and quality DNA required for 1KSA library preparation from 10 µl (1 µl whole blood). A 100 µl blood volume (10 µl whole blood) was tested and produced sufficient yield and quality DNA for downstream processing.

Further testing was carried out on 10, 20 and 50 µl volumes of diluted blood (1, 2 and 5 µl whole blood) from both Parakeet 1 and 2 to determine the lowest suitable volume for extractions with the PureLink™ kit. Results were variable, but EDTA storage produced the best purity values for the DNA, and consistently good DNA yields.

These volumes were tested for Ethanol (Table 2, tubes 1, 2 and 3 for Parakeet 1, and tubes 21, 22 and 23 for Parakeet 2), this treatment produced repeatable results with good quality DNA.

It was not possible to work with volumes for FTA paper so approximate areas of 3 mm², 4 mm² and 5 mm² were used for extractions (Table 2, tubes 25, 26 and 27 for Parakeet 2). This produced low yields with lower than optimal purity values. It was not repeated for Parakeet 1.

The 10, 20 and 50 µl volumes were tested for Acetone (Table 2, tubes 9, 10 and 11 for Parakeet 1, and tubes 29, 30 and 31 for Parakeet 2). The DNA quantity was adequate and consistent, but the A260/A230 ratio was low for Parakeet 1 and high for Parakeet 2 suggesting contamination by organic compounds. DNA from the EDTA tubes (Table 2, tubes 13, 14 and 15 for Parakeet 1, and tubes 33, 34 and 35 for Parakeet 2) had good yields and consistently pure DNA.

DNA/RNA Shield (Table 2, tubes 17, 18 and 19 for Parakeet 1, and tubes 37, 38 and 39 for Parakeet 2) gave DNA with low A260/A280 purity ratios indicating possible protein contamination. The DNA yield was generally good, although two extractions from Parakeet 2 failed, producing no measurable DNA.

A TapeStation assay was carried out on selected DNA samples, to determine intactness and the average DNA fragment size (Table 2).

Table 2: DNA extraction and QC results

Tube #	Treatment	Vol. for extraction	NanoDrop **			Qubit * 1×dsDNA	DNA Yield	Yield per µl of whole blood	TapeStation ^s			
			ng/µl	A260/ 280	A260/ 230	ng/µl	Total ng		DIN ^{ss}	Peak (bp)		
NucleoBond® HMW DNA Kit	3	Parakeet 1 EtOH	~ 250	48.8	1.80	2.15	29.6	4,144	166	9.9	>60,000	
	9	Parakeet 1 ACE	~ 250	234.9	1.86	2.38	580.0	58,000	2,320	9.6	>60,000	
	21	Parakeet 2 EtOH	10	Extraction failed								
		Parakeet 2 EtOH	100	Extraction failed								
	22	Parakeet 2 EtOH	20	-0.8	0.91	0.51	4.2	416	208			
	23	Parakeet 2 EtOH	50	Extraction failed								
	29	Parakeet 2 ACE	10	-0.8	0.87	0.44	3.5	348	348			
	30	Parakeet 2 ACE	20	-0.1	0.96	0.48	4.6	462	231			
	31	Parakeet 2 ACE	50	-1.0	1.04	0.47	2.8	284	57			
	33	Parakeet 2 EDTA	10	2.8	1.63	2.48	2.3	228	228			
		Parakeet 2 EDTA	100	235.8	1.88	2.39	302.0	30,200	3,020	9.7	>60,000	
	34	Parakeet 2 EDTA	20	0.3	-0.35	0.15	2.6	258	129			
	35	Parakeet 2 EDTA	50	Extraction failed								
	39	Parakeet 2 SHE	50	61.1	1.84	2.21	48.6	4,860	972	9.8	>60,000	
PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit	1	Parakeet 1 EtOH	10	16.9	1.86	2.49	12.4	1,240	1,240			
		Parakeet 1 EtOH	100	57.5	1.89	2.37	42.6	4,260	426			
	2	Parakeet 1 EtOH	20	2.1	1.69	-2.32	2.6	264	132			
	3	Parakeet 1 EtOH	50	3.8	1.71	0.76	4.2	416	83	8.7	>60,000	
	9	Parakeet 1 ACE	10	3.5	0.97	0.19	2.9	294	29			
	10	Parakeet 1 ACE	20	8.3	1.66	1.85	22.6	2,260	1,130			
	11	Parakeet 1 ACE	50	14.1	1.78	1.99	17.1	1,710	342	8.8	50,504	
	13	Parakeet 1 EDTA	10	11.7	1.82	2.85	8.8	882	882			
		Parakeet 1 EDTA	100	45.0	1.88	2.36	37.2	3,720	372			
	14	Parakeet 1 EDTA	20	24.8	1.87	2.75	32.0	3,200	1,600			
	15	Parakeet 1 EDTA	50	56.0	1.85	2.30	34.0	3,400	680	8.9	55,130	
	17	Parakeet 1 SHE	10	2.5	1.05	12.98	5.2	518	52			
	18	Parakeet 1 SHE	20	8.0	1.71	2.37	11.0	1,100	550			
	19	Parakeet 1 SHE	50	19.6	1.75	2.63	27.6	2,760	552	9.2	53,048	
	21	Parakeet 2 EtOH	10	23.3	1.83	1.48	15.6	1,560	156			
	22	Parakeet 2 EtOH	20	13.0	1.80	4.25	10.6	1,060	530			
	23	Parakeet 2 EtOH	50	19.4	1.85	2.60	17.5	1,750	350	8.7	53,596	
	25	Parakeet 2 FTA	3mm ²	2.9	2.65	-5.85	6.1	606				
	26	Parakeet 2 FTA	4mm ²	10.8	1.68	0.82	9.1	906				
27	Parakeet 2 FTA	5mm ²	12.1	1.92	1.94	16.7	1,670		6.5	10,981		
29	Parakeet 2 ACE	10	7.0	1.99	100.81	13.5	1,350	135				
30	Parakeet 2 ACE	20	10.2	2.10	4.64	15.5	1,550	775				
31	Parakeet 2 ACE	50	11.1	2.07	3.04	16.2	1,620	324	9.1	55,298		
33	Parakeet 2 EDTA	10	23.3	1.93	2.73	18.4	1,840	184				
34	Parakeet 2 EDTA	20	32.6	1.84	2.83	25.8	2,580	1,290				

Tube #	Treatment	Vol. for extraction	NanoDrop **			Qubit * 1×dsDNA	DNA Yield	Yield per µl of whole blood	TapeStation §	
			ng/µl	A260/ 280	A260/ 230	ng/µl	Total ng		DIN ^{§§}	Peak (bp)
35	Parakeet 2 EDTA	50	49.3	1.86	2.40	38.8	3,880	776	8.6	43,945
37	Parakeet 2 SHE	10	Extraction failed							
38	Parakeet 2 SHE	20	Extraction failed							
39	Parakeet 2 SHE	50	6.5	2.77	5.01	10.0	1,000	200	9.3	>60,000

* Qubit™ 4 Fluorometer Catalog Number Q33226, Invitrogen

(https://assets.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/LSG/manuals/MAN0017209_Qubit_4_Fluorometer_UG.pdf)

** NanoDrop™ One, Thermo Fisher (<https://tools.thermofisher.com/content/sfs/manuals/3091-NanoDrop-One-Help-UG-en.pdf>)

§ Agilent 2200 TapeStation (https://www.agilent.com/cs/library/datasheets/Public/5991-2541EN.pdf?srsltid=AfmBOorgiMeR-YN1TlnZqelVltNkp7WNqXBKYgcIRZMgJB_li6sgy89D)

§§ DIN = DNA Integrity Number. The closer the number to 10, the more intact the DNA.

EtOH: Ethanol; FTA: FTA paper; ACE: Acetone; EDTA: Purple EDTA blood tube; SHE: DNA/RNA Shield

DNA Quality Control

DNA concentration was analysed by Qubit 1 × dsDNA Broad Range Assay (https://documents.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/LSG/manuals/MAN0019617_Qubit_1X_dsDNA_BR_Assay_UG.pdf).

DNA purity was analysed on the NanoDrop™ One (<https://tools.thermofisher.com/content/sfs/manuals/3091-NanoDrop-One-Help-UG-en.pdf>).

DNA integrity was analysed on an Agilent 2200 TapeStation using a Genomic DNA ScreenTape assay (https://www.agilent.com/cs/library/usermanuals/public/gDNA_QuickGuide.pdf?srsltid=AfmBOopnghMVo0wmtvH2d7GTAYNnT4WPVYvD3gbMc8DtLt3JZO4HKvqS).

The electropherograms from the TapeStation analysis are shown in Figure 2 below. The peaks detected by the TapeStation were all above 50 000 bp, except for the FTA paper with had a DNA peak at 10 981 bp indicating some DNA degradation. The DNA extractions using the NucleoBond® HMW DNA kit had peaks above 60 000 bp, illustrated by the “DNA/RNA Shield & Nucleobond” electropherogram in Figure 2. This is out of the range of the assay, and the size cannot be determined. DNA of this size requires shearing before sequencing library preparation.

Figure 2: Agilent TapeStation Genomic DNA ScreenTape assay electropherograms showing DNA integrity for DNA extracted from Ethanol, FTA paper, Acetone, EDTA blood tubes and DNA/RNA Shield storage methods using the PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit. Additionally the NucleoBond® HMW DNA Kit DNA extracted from the DNA/RNA Shield method is shown.

ONT Library Preparation & Sequencing

ONT sequencing libraries were made using the Ligation Sequencing Kit XL V14 (<https://nanoporetech.com/document/ligation-sequencing-gdna-sqk-lsk114-xl>) and run on the PromethION 24 sequencer. The PromethION flow cells used for sequencing were past their expiry dates, but still showed the sequencing libraries performance and quality during the runs.

The EDTA and Ethanol storage methods with extraction using the PureLink™ kit produced DNA with good sequencing results. Table 3 below shows the sequencing data and QC metrics. The N50 values were good (>10 kb) for these EDTA and Ethanol. N50 values represent the length of the shortest read from the longest sequences that represent >50% of the nucleotides in the sequencing run. The EDTA and Ethanol storage methods also had the highest data output per available pore (sequencing capacity of flow cell). The FTA paper method produced a short sequencing library size with a low N50, confirming that DNA extracted from FTA paper is not suitable for nanopore sequencing. The DNA/RNA Shield method, coupled with the Purelink DNA extraction, produced sequencing data with only 2% of the reads passing quality control, indicating that a carry-over compound in the DNA killed the sequencing

pores and the sequencing run reached end-of-life very fast. However, the DNA/RNA Shield method with extraction using the NucleoBond® kit produced good sequence data. The DNA was not sheared before library preparation for this NucleoBond® extraction. This run used the best quality flow cell, the number of pores listed in Table 3 indicate sequencing flow cell health.

Table 3: Sequencing output and QC

Sample/ Treatment	Ave library size (kb)	N50	Total data (Gb)	Passed data (Gb)	Passed/ total reads (%)	Gb/1K pores	* Flow cell pores	Total run time
PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit								
Ethanol	26.6	10.25	6.69	5.62	84%	4.18	1600	15 hr 11 min
FTA paper 5 mm	16	5.71	0.39	0.294	75%	0.37	1065	1 hr 54 min
Acetone	27.9	10.88	4.93	3.65	74%	2.90	1700	11 hr 59 min
EDTA	21.6	13.57	11.26	9.21	82%	4.17	2700	15 hr 13 min
DNA/RNA Shield	29.5	12	0.097	0.088	2%	0.09	1018	22 min
NucleoBond® HMW DNA Kit								
DNA/RNA Shield	30.1	21.21	29.06	25.03	86%	6.27	4633	27 hr 23 min

* number of pores available indicates sequencing flow cell health

Extraction Kit Costs

Macherey-Nagel NucleoBond® HMW DNA Kit

R4123.24 excl. VAT for 20 reactions

This works out to **R206.16 per extraction** (excl. VAT), not taking consumables into consideration

Quote date: 2026/03/16

Supplier: Separations

Invitrogen PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit

R2910.00 excl. VAT for 50 reactions

This works out to **R58.20 per extraction** (excl. VAT), not taking consumables into consideration

Quote date: 2026/03/10

Supplier: LTC Tech South Africa Pty LTD

Conclusions

Small volumes of blood

Store blood in an EDTA tube or dilute blood in Ethanol and use the PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit for DNA extractions. It's advisable to split a volume of 5 µl of whole blood (50 µl of blood diluted 1:10) between two extractions and to use the smallest elution volume the manufacturers recommend and pool the DNA. This is because lower volumes of input blood yield more DNA per µl of blood.

Large volumes of blood (>10 µl)

Use the PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit for DNA extractions as above. Alternatively, use the NucleoBond® HMW DNA kit with a higher input volume of blood and transfer the Isopropanol precipitation to 1.5 ml tubes for centrifugation at ~11 000 × g. Ten (10) and 25 µl of whole blood (250 µl of blood diluted 1:10) were shown to work. The NucleoBond® kit produces DNA of higher molecular weight/integrity, however the higher molecular weight DNA will need to be sheared for optimal sequencing.

Conclusion

The PureLink™ Genomic DNA Mini Kit is cost effective, time efficient and easy to use. It produced the best DNA yield, NanoDrop purity ratios and sequencing N50 for 50 µl volumes (5 µl whole blood) of EDTA stored blood diluted 1:10. This was repeatable for Parakeet 1 and 2. There was sufficient DNA to prepare 2 libraries if data output needs to be increased by washing and reloading the flow cell. For smaller birds, 20 µl (2 µl whole blood) can be used, but only one sequencing library can be produced. This should not be a problem as the average bird genome size is about 1.0 to 1.3 Gb and one sequencing run can produce enough data for a 3.1 Gb genome.

Ethanol and Acetone can also be used, but 50 µl volumes (5 µl whole blood) are recommended.

If DNA/RNA Shield is the only available storage option, the NucleoBond® kit should be used for DNA extraction. We observed that the DNA extracted with this method sequenced well. However, the sequencing library prepared from DNA extracted using the PureLink™ kit caused the sequencing flow cell to run to end-of-life abnormally fast. This has been reported for DNA/RNA Shield-stored samples by others as well.

FTA paper is not recommended for storage of blood for long read sequencing. The DNA had lower integrity than all other methods, resulting in a sequencing N50 below 10 kb.